

Emerging Challenges, July 2019

Libya: civil war or proxy war?

Recently, a new major fight has erupted around Tripoli. Eastern Libya leader Khalifa Haftar, who has since 4 April tried to seize Tripoli by sheer force, has launched a second offensive on the capital held by the UN-recognised Government of Fayeze al-Sarraj (GNA). Codenamed Zero Hour, the attack has met with fierce resistance by GNA forces and the Western militias supporting Sarraj. As the battle shrinks into another stalemate, statistics by the World Health Organization (WHO) set Libyan civilian and military casualties at 1093 dead and 5700 wounded since April, with an estimated 100,000 people displaced. Migrants stuck in Libya also took their toll, as Haftar's air forces bombed on 2 July (possibly by accident) the Tajoura detention centre, killing 44 migrants and wounding over 130. Some international observers now openly refer to the crisis a civil war – the second in eight years, if the anti-Gaddafi revolt is considered as such. But to what extent are the drivers of the Libyan conflict domestic, and to what extent are they external?

Both Sarraj and Haftar reject the notion of civil war. The former holds he is facing a rebellion by Haftar; the latter calls it a liberation from the corrupt and inept GNA. Behind their clash lay longer-lasting factors. First, a struggle over governance, influenced by the traditional disunity of the Libyan society – fragmented in tribes and along the centre-periphery and East-West divides; aggravated by Ghaddafi's dismantling of the Libyan state (and the Libyan army), this encouraged a progressive polarisation of the political landscape since 2011, epitomised by militias' competition. In this context, Haftar presents himself as the strong man of order, claiming he is leading a national army – whereas he is in fact heavily relying on militias and foreign fighters. GNA supporters simply consider him a new Ghaddafi.

Yet the struggle between Libyan factions might have ended in mutual exhaustion by now, had it not been fuelled by external actors. Egypt, the UAE, and Saudi Arabia have aided Haftar with weapons and at times air power – in open violation of UN resolutions; Turkey, Qatar and Sudan back the

GNA. Greater powers are also involved. Russia and, more recently, the US have been sympathetic to Haftar, whereas the EU is in theory behind the GNA, though some of its member states like France have given Haftar considerable political support. Divided, the UN Security Council has no leverage to call for – and enforce – a ceasefire. Thus, foreign influence is expanding and prolonging the conflict.

A protracted war of attrition would have a traumatic impact on both Libya and the broader region, possibly leading to a militarisation of Libyan oil infrastructures, an increasing competition for – and looting of – the country's resources, an expansion of the already rambling illicit transnational businesses, and a revival of migration flows. Finally, the chaos and the power vacuum are giving a new life to Daesh in Fezzan.

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